

The Implementation of Budget Based on Performance in Improving the Performance of Local Government Sub Sites Datuk Bandar Tanjung Balai

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Abstract: Performance-Based on a budget (CREW) can be interpreted as a form of the budget resources that are connected with the results from the ministry of the level of government. The budget itself is drafted based on the approach of performance-oriented towards the output. The budget cycle is the period or the period starts when the budget is drawn up until the time of the calculation of the budget passed with the laws. The budget cycle consists of several stages (phase) namely: preparation stage, Stage Ratification, implementation phase, and levels of reporting and evaluation. This research done on the entire office is in the sub-district Datuk Bandar, Tanjung Balai. The purpose of this research is to know how the implementation of budget based on performance in improving the performance of Local Government with the case study in Datuk Bandar Tanjung Balai. Data retrieved using questioner on that acquired from the User of the Power Budget and the treasurer on 5 subs and 1 sub-districts in the sub-district Datuk Bandar City Tanjung Balai and then the data is processed using the methods of descriptive methods analytically with qualitative approach. The results of this study mention that the entire performance-based budget activities including planning, implementation, reporting, and evaluation as a form of performance improvement in all institutions that there is in a sub-district Datuk Bandar, Tanjung Balai who have been appropriate or run well.

Keywords: Planning of Budget, Implementation of budget, Budget Reporting, and evaluation of the budget and the performance of the Regional Government on the SKPD.

I. Introduction

In the implementation of the regional budget, management is a process that requires the involvement of all layers of the society and gave power to the local government in the conduct of the regional financial management so that the role of the government is as a catalyst and facilitator for the government that has more knowledge development goals and objectives that will be achieved. as catalysts and facilitators because the government is more aware of development goals and objectives that will be achieved as catalysts and facilitators would need various means and supporting facilities in the framework of the implementation of sustainable development.

Government institutions as mandated in the Constitution, claimed the existence of a change in mindset to arrange a program, and designing activities of the budget is based on the orientation to achieve one purpose. The management of the money countries following Law No.17 2003 stipulates that in the draft budget for the government agencies must be oriented to the performance. This is strengthened by Mardiasmo (2001) stated that in the formulation of the regional budget that he wills is: (a) Regional Budget must be hinged on public interests; (b) Regional Budget must be managed with good results and low cost (work better and cost less); (c) Regional Budget must be able to provide greater transparency and accountability in the rationale for the entire budget cycle; (d) Regional Budget must be managed with the performance approach (performance-oriented) for all kinds of expenses and income; (e) Regional budget must be able to grow in the professionalism of the work in each organization related; (f) Regional Budget must be able to provide more freedom for the provided to maximize funds with attention to the principle of value for money.

Now the formulation of problems in the design of this research is how the implementation of the budget based on the performance measured based on planning, implementation of reporting, and evaluation in improving the performance of local government, especially at Sub-Bandar Tanjung Balai.

The objective of this research is to know how the implementation of the budget based on the performance measured based on planning, implementation, reporting, and evaluation in improving the performance of local government, especially at Sub-Bandar Tanjung Balai.

II. Literature Review

In the (Sinambela, 2003) mentioned that participation in the formulation of consideration as a managerial approach that can improve the performance of the organization. The subordinates who feel their aspirations appreciated and had an effect on the budget is compiled will have more responsibility and moral consequences that improve the performance of appropriately targeted in the budget.

III. Methodology

The research carried out in this research is using descriptive methods analytically with a qualitative approach. The use of this approach will be adjusted with the main objective of the research, namely describes and analyzes regarding the performance of the government at subsites Datuk Bandar Tanjung Balai.

Something which becomes operational parameters variable in this research is the implementation of a Performance-Based budget with the budget planning indicator, budget implementation, budget reporting, evaluation and budget and Government performance planning, investigations, market coordination., evaluation, supervision, staff settings, negotiations, representatives and overall performance.

The population in this research is the entire samples will be observed namely from the Treasurer Budget Power Users in both the environment and the entire Sub-district in Datuk Bandar as many as 20 the respondents and also supported by other data sources in the form of an interview statement to support the results of research.

The source of the data in the laboratory is the primary data. Primary data is a research data source obtained directly from the source. The Data from the User Power Budget, general bursar, Treasurer of acceptance, and Treasurer of the expenses that have been collected using the research instrument in the form of the questionnaire in the form of the answer is closed.

Using descriptive methods analytically with a qualitative approach, the first questionnaire test is done namely validity test and rehabilitates test. Then the use of this approach will be adjusted with the main objective of the research, namely describes and analyzes regarding the performance of the sub-district government Datuk Bandar. The technique of Data Collection on the implementation of the budget based on the performance of using the structured questionnaire consists of questions covered in the form of a list of statements that provided or distributed to the respondents to be filled based on the perception of each respondents using 9 questions for planning, 3 questions for the implementation of the Budget Implementation/ 3 questions for reporting and 3 questions for evaluation. While on the variable government performance on Kecamatan Datuk Bandar using 7 questions. The data collected were analyzed with test chi-square. This test aims to know how far the implementation of the budget based on the performance against the performance of the Government. With the performance of the sub-District Government Datuk Bandar with the level of the true meaning of p less than 0.05. The formulation of the true meaning of p less than 0.05 means to show that there is a significant impact between the implementation of the budget based on the performance with the performance of the Government.

IV. Results

Validity test results which are not all r count greater r table. Where the value of r the table to sample as many as 20 in 0,359 as can be illustrated in table 1 below:

Table 1. Validity Test

Perencanaan Anggaran	Pertanyaan 1	0,924	0,359	Valid
	Pertanyaan 2	0,784	0,359	Valid
	Pertanyaan 3	0,709	0,359	Valid
	Pertanyaan 4	0,873	0,359	Valid
	Pertanyaan 5	0,898	0,359	Valid
	Pertanyaan 6	0,587	0,359	Valid
	Pertanyaan 7	0,724	0,359	Valid
	Pertanyaan 8	0,770	0,359	Valid
	Pertanyaan 9	0,918	0,359	Valid
Pelaksanaan Anggaran	Pertanyaan 1	0,929	0,359	Valid
	Pertanyaan 2	0,923	0,359	Valid
	Pertanyaan 3	0,875	0,359	Valid
Pelaporan Anggaran	Pertanyaan 1	0,961	0,359	Valid
	Pertanyaan 2	0,933	0,359	Valid
	Pertanyaan 3	0,944	0,359	Valid
Evaluasi Anggaran	Pertanyaan 1	0,891	0,359	Valid
	Pertanyaan 2	0,817	0,359	Valid
	Pertanyaan 3	0,876	0,359	Valid
Kinerja Aparatur Pemerintah	Pertanyaan 1	0,467	0,422	Valid
	Pertanyaan 2	0,569	0,422	Valid
	Pertanyaan 3	0,748	0,422	Valid
	Pertanyaan 4	0,557	0,422	Valid
	Pertanyaan 5	0,485	0,422	Valid
	Pertanyaan 6	0,492	0,422	Valid
	Pertanyaan 7	0,530	0,422	Valid

The reliability of a change of variables is said well if it has the value of *Cronbach's Errs* > 0.60. From Realiabilitas questioner, questions which have been submitted to the authors of the respondents in this research will be visible on the table *Reliability Statistic* that is served on table 2 :

Table 2. Reabilitas Test

Variabel	<i>Alpha Cronbach's</i>	Batas Reliabilitas	Ket
Perencanaan Anggaran	0,783	0,6	Realibel
Pelaksanaan Anggaran	0,865	0,6	Realibel
Pelaporan Anggaran	0,874	0,6	Realibel
Evaluasi Anggaran	0,849	0,6	Realibel
Kinerja Pemerintah	0,713	0,6	Realibel

Based on the table above can be seen on each - each item varies with the statement, it is known that the value of *Cronbach's Alpha* > 0.60, so it can be concluded that the change of the statement through the questionnaire about budget planning, implementation of the budget, Budget Reporting Budget Evaluation and performance of the Government is reliable and acceptable.

Data relating to the achievement of the performance of the government in the sub-district Datuk Bandar explained in table 3 below :

Table 3. Performance of The Government in The Sub-District Datuk Bandar

KINERJA PEMERINTAH				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid CUKUP	1	5.0	5.0	5.0
BAIK	19	95.0	95.0	100.0
Total	20	100.0	100.0	

From the table above it is known that a small part of the respondents i.e. 5 percent mentioned the performance of the Government enough and almost all respondents namely 95% stated the performance of the Government.

The influence of the implementation of Performance-Based Budget in improving the performance of Local Government analyzed with test Chi-Square with the level of statistical significance $\alpha = \leq 0.05$. Cross tests conducted on the relationship between the planning, implementation, reporting, and evaluation of accountability performance. Each will be explained in the next chapter.

The influence of budget planning in improving the performance of the Government in the sub-district Datuk Bandar can be seen in the table below.

Table 4. Crosstab Planning Influence in Improving the Performance of The Government

PERENCANAAN_ANGGARAN * KINERJA_PEMERINTAH Crosstabulation

Count		KINERJA_PEMERINTAH		Total
		CUKUP	YA	
PERENCANAAN_ANGGARAN	CUKUP	0	4	4
	YA	1	15	16
Total		1	19	20

From the table 4.4.1 known that there are 4 people respondents who have enough budget planning but the performance of its government according (O) and 1 of the planning of the budget has been appropriate but having enough government performance and deals as much as 15 people according to the budget planning (O) in line with the performance of its rulers. To know the influence of budget planning for the performance of the government can be known from the data test Chi-Square on table 5 below :

Table 5. Test The Chi-Square

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.263 ^a	1	.608		
Continuity Correction ^b	.000	1	1.000		
Likelihood Ratio	.459	1	.498		
Fisher's Exact Test				1.000	.800
Linear-by-Linear Association	.250	1	.617		
N of Valid Cases ^b	20				

a. 3 cells (75,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,20.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

On the table Chi-Square test, Pearson Chi-Square line indicates the price α 0,263 (a), Indonesia Recorded It's $94 = 2$, and p -value = 0,608 > 0,005, means no influence between budget planning with the performance of the government in the sub-district environment Datuk Bandar. Next, to know the level of budget planning influence on the performance with the performance of the government in the sub-district Datuk Bandar elaborated on table 6 below.

Table 6. Symmetric Measures

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Contingency Coefficient	.114	.608
N of Valid Cases		20	

In table 6 obtained *greatly enhanced* by 0,114 contingency value that shows the level of budget planning influence on the performance of the government of low value means the influence of budget planning for the performance of the government in the sub-district Datuk Bandar according to the opinion of respondents is low.

Table 7. Crosstab Implementation Influence in Improving the Performance of The Government

PELAKSANAAN_ANGGARAN * KINERJA_PEMERINTAH Crosstabulation

Count

		KINERJA_PEMERINTAH		Total
		CUKUP	YA	
PELAKSANAAN_ANGGARAN	TIDAK	1	2	3
	CUKUP	0	1	1
	YA	0	16	16
Total		1	19	20

From table 7 know that there are 1 of the respondents that the implementation of the budget is not good but the performance in its rulers is enough and 2 the implementation of the budget is not good but the performance of its government according (O). Then there is 1 of the implementation of direct funding for AI will decrease enough but the performance of its government according (O). Deals as much as 16 the implementation of the appropriate budget and its performance is also appropriate(O). To find out the influence of the implementation of the budget on the performance of the government can be known from the data test Chi-Square on table 8 below:

Table 8. Test The Chi-Square

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.965 ^a	2	.051
Likelihood Ratio	4.122	2	.127
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.161	1	.023
N of Valid Cases	20		

a. 5 cells (83,3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,05.

On the table Chi-Square test, Pearson Chi-Square line indicates the price α 5,965 (a), Indonesia Recorded It's 94 = 2, and p-value = 0,051 > 0,005, means no influence between the implementation of the budget with the performance of the government in the sub-district environment Datuk Bandar. Next to know the level of implementation which influences the budget with the performance of the government in the sub-district Datuk Bandar elaborated on table 8.

Table 9. Symmetric Measures

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Contingency Coefficient	.479	.051
N of Valid Cases		20	

On table 9, obtained *greatly enhanced* by 0,479 contingency value that shows the level of budget implementation influence it against government performance worth just means the influence of the implementation of the budget to the performance of the government in the sub-district Datuk Bandar according to the opinion of the respondents this is enough.

Table 10. The Influence of the Crosstab

PELAPORAN_ANGGARAN * KINERJA_PEMERINTAH Crosstabulation

Count		KINERJA_PEMERINTAH		Total
		CUKUP	YA	
PELAPORAN_ANGGARAN	TIDAK	0	3	3
	CUKUP	1	3	4
	YA	0	13	13
Total		1	19	20

From table 10 know that there are 3 people of respondents reporting the budget is not good but the performance in its rulers according (O). Then there is 1 person reporting enough direct funding for AI will decrease but the performance of its rulers also enough and 3 the reporting budget enough but the performance of his reign according (O). Deals as much as 13 the appropriate budget reporting and its performance is also appropriate (O). To know the influence of budget reporting on the performance of the government can be known from the data test Chi-Square on table 10 below :

Table 11. The influence of Budget reporting on the performance of the Government Datuk Bandar

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4.211 ^a	2	.122
Likelihood Ratio	3.442	2	.179
Linear-by-Linear Association	.455	1	.500
N of Valid Cases	20		

a. 5 cells (83,3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,15.

On the table Chi-Square test, Pearson Chi-Square line indicates the price α 4,211 (a), Indonesia Recorded It's $94 = 2$, and $p\text{-value} = 0,122 > 0,005$, means no influence between budget reporting with the performance of the government in the sub-district environment at Datuk Bandar. Next to know the level of budget reporting influence with the performance of the government in the sub-district Datuk Bandar elaborated on table 12 below.

Table 12. Symmetric Measures

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Contingency Coefficient	.417	.122
N of Valid Cases		20	

On table 12 Symmetric Measures obtained greatly enhanced by 0,417 contingency value that shows the level of budget reporting influence on the performance of the government enough value means the influence of the implementation of the budget to the performance of the government in the sub-district Datuk Bandar according to the opinion of the respondents.

Table 13. Crosstab Budget Evaluation influence in improving the performance of the Government

EVALUASI_ANGGARAN * KINERJA_PEMERINTAH Crosstabulation

Count		KINERJA_PEMERINTAH		Total
		CUKUP	YA	
EVALUASI_ANGGARAN	CUKUP	1	7	8
	YA	0	12	12
Total		1	19	20

From table 13 know that there are 1 people, respondents, enough budget evaluation, and performance in its rulers enough. Then there is 7 evaluation of the direct funding for AI that will decrease enough but the performance of its government according (O). Then there is 12 evaluation of the appropriate budget (O) and the performance of his reign according (O). To know the influence of budget reporting on the performance of the government can be known from the data test Chi-Square on table 14 below :

Table 14. Test The Chi-Square

Chi-Square Tests					
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.579 ^a	1	.209		
Continuity Correction ^b	.044	1	.834		
Likelihood Ratio	1.912	1	.167		
Fisher's Exact Test				.400	.400
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.500	1	.221		
N of Valid Cases ^a	20				

a. 2 cells (50,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .40.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

On the table Chi-Square test, Pearson Chi-Square line indicates the price α 1,579 (a), Indonesia Recorded It's 94 = 1, and p-value = 0,209 > 0,005, means no influence between the evaluation of the budget with the performance of the government in the sub-district environment Datuk Bandar. Next to know the level of budget evaluation influence with the performance of the government in the sub-district Datuk Bandar elaborated on table 15 below.

Table 15. Symmetric Measures

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Contingency Coefficient	.271	.209
N of Valid Cases		20	

On table 15, obtained *greatly enhanced* by the 0,271 contingency value that shows the level of influence budget evaluation of government performance low value means the influence of budget evaluation of the performance of the government in the sub-district Datuk Bandar according to the opinion of respondents is low.

Budget planning arranged to ensure that development activities run effective, efficient, and accurate. The overall regional budget planning includes the formulation of Public Policy the budget acceptance and Regional Budget (APBD) until he arranges the Draft State Budget acceptance and Regional Budget (APBD) consists of several stages of the planning process the regional budget. The weak relationship between budget planning performance based on the performance of the government normally at Sub-Bandar shows that the function of the planning structural officials in the sub-district sites Datuk Bandar weak despite their commitment to the purpose of very high organization. This is proved by the results of research mentioned that although they were weak in the planning the performance of the ruling was high.

The implementation of the budget covers the implementation of budget revenues, shopping, and financing. The implementation of the budget conducted after the implementation of the work unit budget Document Regional Device (DPA claims the SKPD) specified by the Regional Financial Management Officials (PPKD) with the approval of the Regional Secretary (Sekda). The implementation of the budget involves many more people than the preparation and consider feedback from the experience of truth.

The influence of the implementation of the budget based on the performance against the performance of the Government valuable enough performance on District sites Bandar Grandparents related to the division of tasks on structural officials where the existence of the division activities which are not following the main task and function. This may be caused by a shortage of personnel who have sufficient qualifications and competencies and aligned so that despite its main duty and function is in the scope of the office but in the implementation of the budget respondent does not contribute to a little so that they respond to the implementation of the budget for its performance is appropriate.

Report the implementation of the budget conducted periodically that includes a document the implementation of the budget (DPA claims) in all sub-district environment is a task that Datuk Bandar from the finance section so will be fair only when respondents stated that the relationship between the budget implementation reports with the performance of the government.

Performance Evaluation is to assess the activities or see the success and failure of an organization or work unit in carrying out the tasks and functions of the burden. The purpose of performance evaluation is done so that the organization that person knows the achievement of realization, progress, and obstacles that found or for not achieving the performance to achieve the mission that has been planned so that it is expected that the institution can improve its performance in the future. Performance Evaluation of the weak enough budget affects the performance of the Sub-district sites Datuk Bandar which means to show that structural officials have less commitment to always do the budget evaluation periodically. This is shown by 7 of the respondents expressed to do a budget evaluation in enough categories.

V. Conclusion

From the explanation and analysis of the previous chapters and the authors conclude about Budget Implementation Performance based on the Sub-Datuk Bandar as follows. From the planning factor known as much as 4 respondents expressed its involvement in the form of budget planning and most respondents 16 the states involved in planning the budget which is appropriate or good. From the implementation of factors known small part of respondents 3 said that its involvement and the implementation of the budget are not good, a small part of 1, the involvement of the implementation of the budget states good enough and as many as 16 people said that the involvement in the implementation of the budget has been appropriate or good. From the reporting factors known small part of 3 the respondents expressed its involvement budget reporting is not good then as much as 4 of the respondents expressed its involvement budget reporting which is good enough and most respondents namely 13 people said that their involvement reporting budget has been appropriate or good. From the evaluation factors known most respondents namely, 8 people said that their involvement in the evaluation of the budget nearly enough and the majority of respondents as much as 12 people said that his involvement Evaluation budget has already been appropriate or good. Then from the explanation above, it can be concluded that the entire performance-based budget activities including planning, implementation, reporting, and evaluation as a form of performance improvement in all institutions that there is a sub-district Datuk Bandar, Tanjung Balai have been appropriate or run well.

From an explanation of the conclusion that has been presented so, a writer can provide suggestions/inputs for the direction of all the environment at sub-district Datuk Bandar as follows he role of each Structural Officials should be more optimized in planning, implementation, reporting and evaluation of the budget as part of the effort to raise the performance. The sub-district government should make technical guidance on structural officials related to the intensive budget.

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